

Comfort-aware Energy Management for Elderly Residents

ABSTRACT

The Italian pilot demonstrates how **comfort-aware energy management** can support residential demand response in a **senior cohousing setting**. Combining environmental monitoring, a digital twin and an **AI-driven comfort-based flexibility model**, it addresses elderly users and centralised building management. The pilot shows that DR in vulnerable-user contexts requires **accessible, low-barrier engagement formats** and the vital mediation of **on-site care staff** to bridge the digital divide.

KEY POINTS

- Deploying interoperable Digital Twins to seamlessly visualise real-time environmental conditions and optimise building-level flexibility without disrupting resident routines.
- Combining comfort-based flexibility models with tailored, accessible feedback mechanisms to ensure optimal well-being for elderly residents.
- Successfully validating human-centric energy services within a highly centralised, vulnerable-user senior cohousing facility.
- Useful lessons for mediated residential DR deployment that strictly prioritises occupant health.

The pilot is implemented at **Borgo Mazzini Smart Cohousing in Treviso**, which hosts nearly 80 residents. Within DEDALUS, activities focus on **16 apartments** and on the residential test cluster of **Casa Maddalena**, where **3 rooms** were used to validate comfort-aware digital energy services under real operating conditions.

INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES AND SERVICES

The Italian pilot combines interoperable tools supporting monitoring, comfort assessment and personalised flexibility services:

- **IoT Platform & Monitoring Ecosystem**, a comprehensive network of 3-phase energy meters, Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) sensors (tracking CO₂ and humidity), and light sensors enabling precise, apartment-level environmental monitoring.
- **Comfort Flexibility Model**, an AI-driven engine that harmonises occupant comfort with energy efficiency, generating three daily optimisation strategies (Comfort-oriented, Balanced, and Energy-oriented) based on residents' actual Thermal Sensation Votes (TSV).
- **Digital Twin**, providing building managers with an interactive dashboard that displays real-time comfort data, energy consumption simulations, and actionable day-ahead DR recommendations.

ENGAGEMENT

- Successfully engaged **20 elderly residents** by adapting to their specific psychophysical needs, utilising **on-site psychologists and nursing staff** as vital "engagement ambassadors" to build trust and facilitate participation.
- The residential engagement format was adapted to the elderly residents' profile, with a **modified questionnaire focused on comfort** and the option to answer on paper rather than digitally.
- The pilot organised **two technical workshops**: one for three professional participants at ISRAA's technical office and one for six residential participants at the cohousing site.
- The residential discussion worked best when framed around **comfort, health and wellbeing**, while the professional audience showed interest but also some resistance regarding immediate operational applicability.
- The pilot highlighted the importance of **early promotion, realistic mock-ups** and the **role of care staff** as mediators between technologies and end users.

AUTHORS

Ilaria Orfino

Fondazione ICONS

Panos Skaloumpakas

NTUA

LEARN MORE ABOUT DEDALUS PROJECT

www.dedalus-horizon.eu

info@dedalus-horizon.eu

Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement No. 101103998.

● KEY RESULTS

- By basing recommendations on actual resident feedback, the pilot successfully reduced **temperature-related complaints** against a high historical baseline of thermal dissatisfaction, where 33% of households experienced complaints in the summer and 57% in the winter.
- **Achieved a 29.05% ratio of exploited versus planned flexibility**, confirming that the system successfully triggers load shifting.
- Delivered net **reduction in energy consumption of 1.78%** over a five-day validation period testing at the Casa Maddalena cluster.

● REPLICATION RELEVANCE

- The Italian pilot provides a relevant use case for residential DR services in **vulnerable-user contexts**.
- Replication should combine **environmental monitoring, comfort modelling and digital twin functionality** within one coherent operational framework.
- In elderly or mediated living environments, energy optimisation should be aligned with users' **subjective comfort** and supported by accessible, low-barrier engagement formats.

● RECOMMENDATIONS

- Residential DR services for vulnerable users should combine **energy monitoring, environmental sensing and personalised comfort assessment**.
- **Comfort** should be treated as a core operational parameter, especially in senior living environments where wellbeing and usability are central.
- **Digital twins and comfort-based flexibility models** can support more adaptive residential energy management, but their value should be communicated through realistic use cases and mediated support.
- User-friendly interfaces alone are not enough: vulnerable-user contexts benefit from **care staff involvement, paper-based alternatives and communication framed around comfort** rather than technical optimisation.

REFERENCES

D5.4: DEDALUS impact and social acceptance analysis, 2026